

International Conference on
Quantum Theory:
Reconsideration of Foundations - 4

International Center for
Mathematical Modelling in Physics,
Engineering and Cognitive Sciences

Växjö University, Sweden
June 11-16, 2007

List of Abstracts

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Is the moon there when nobody looks?

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(joint work with Andrei Khrennikov)

In 1981, David Mermin described a cleverly simplified version of Bell's theorem. It pointed out in a straightforward way that interpreting entanglement from a local realist point of view can be problematic. We propose here an extended version of Mermin's device that can actually be given a simple local realist interpretation, and we argue that we still have no scientific reason to believe that the moon could possibly not be there when nobody looks.

Bell's Theorem - A fallacy of the excluded middle.

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Albert Einstein never really accepted quantum mechanics. According to Einstein, quantum mechanics is not a complete physical theory. Einstein's dissatisfaction with quantum mechanics intrinsic randomness lead to the famous Einstein, Podolsky and Rosen thought experiment and the Einstein Podolsky Rosen paradox (EPR paradox) which assumes local realism. The Einstein, Podolsky and Rosen thought experiment was the origin of J. S. Bell's publication in 1964. After the publication of Bell's theorem, a variety of experiments were devised to test Bell's inequalities. The first experimental test of Bell's inequality was performed by Freedman and Clauser (1972). Some dramatic violations of Bell's inequality have been reported by so called Bell test experiments. This is taken as empirical evidence against local realism and as positive evidence in favour of quantum mechanics. It is claimed that under local realist theories Bell inequalities cannot be violated. Contrary to this, quantum mechanics predicts that the Bell inequalities will be violated. Who is right, who is wrong? Does quantum mechanics exclude local realism and thus relativity and vice versa? Are there local realist hopes for quantum mechanics besides of Bell's theorem? However, does parameters exist whether they are measured or not, does measurement disturbs the thing being measured. Nonetheless, the time has come to close the book completely on Bell's theorem. The purpose of this contribution is to refute Bell's theorem definitely by the proof that Bell's theorem is a fallacy of the excluded middle.

Quantum Mechanics as Approximation of Statistical Mechanics of Classical Fields: order of Approximation

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We show that the mathematical formalism of the quantum statistical model can be interpreted as a method for approximation of classical (measure-theoretic) averages on the infinite-dimensional phase space. The technique of approximation is based on the Taylor expansion of functionals of classical fields. To find the order of the deviation of quantum statistical predictions from the classical predictions, we use the time-scaling arguments. We show that quantum randomness might be considered as the result of random fluctuations at the Planck time-scale.

EPR Paradox, locality and completeness of Quantum Theory

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The quantum theory (QT) and new stochastic approaches have no deterministic prediction for a single measurement or for a single time-series of events observed for a trapped ion, electron or any other individual physical system. The predictions of QT being of probabilistic character appear in the statistical distribution of the results obtained in various experiments. The Copenhagen interpretation (CI) of QT acknowledged the abstract and statistical character of the predictions at QT but at the same time claimed that a state vector provided complete description of each individual physical system. Einstein, Podolski and Rosen (EPR) disagreed with this claim and concluded that the probabilistic predictions of QT should be derived from some more fundamental spatio-temporal deterministic description of the invisible sub-phenomena. The experimental violation of the Bell inequalities in the spin polarization correlation experiments (SPCE) which were the implementations of Bohm and EPR gedanken experiments eliminated so called local realistic models of the sub-phenomena. The violation of these inequalities was often incorrectly interpreted as a proof of the completeness of QT or the violation of locality and causality in the macro-world. It was overlooked that the probability distribution is not an attribute of a dice but is only a characteristic of a whole random experiment: "tolling a dice". Therefore the quantum probabilities do not describe the lack of knowledge about the attributes of physical systems but the lack of knowledge about the experiments and in this sense they are "contextual". Moreover any mathematical probabilistic model used to describe a random experiment is consistent only with a specific protocol telling how the random experiment has to be performed. The probabilistic models used to prove Bell inequalities implied a protocol inappropriate and impossible to implement for SPCE. Therefore the question whether QT is predictably complete is still open and it should be answered by a careful and unconventional analysis of the experimental data. The current understanding of statistical and contextual character of QT will have as far reaching consequences for the quantum information and quantum computing.

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